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Commission

Technology Monitoring and Assessment

Comparing EU, US and Chinese approaches

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Technology Monitoring and Assessment: Comparing EU, US and Chinese approaches

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EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Technology Monitoring and Assessment

Comparing EU, US and Chinese approaches

Policy brief

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INTRODUCTION¹

Disruptive technologies have driven economic, social and political transformation at various moments in human history. Perez (2002, 2009, 2015) identifies five “technological revolutions” which unleashed what she calls “great surges” in economic and social development as well as in the distribution of military might and, more generally, hard and soft power between countries and regions.²

There is evidence that when falling behind in certain key technologies, this gap is likely to increase.³ The development of technology gaps, particularly in key technologies, thus risks creating a self-reinforcing dynamic. A related consequence of such technology gaps is that the cost the laggard country or region has to pay to acquire or gain access to the technology in question also tends to increase (Cantner, 2023). In particular, Cantner (2023) notes that “in the lagging economies, the reduced availability of the key technology and its higher price will constrain the process of improving goods in all industries that use the key technology as an input. Consequently, the process of generating new knowledge in these industries slows, leading to a further deterioration of the terms of trade”. In the current era of geopolitical friction, competition over the mastery of key technologies and concerns over technological sovereignty, preventing and closing technology gaps becomes particularly important.

Technology anticipation through monitoring and foresight has been shown to improve crisis anticipation and management, both with regards to unforeseen catastrophic events such as COVID (“black swans”) and foreseeable but unavoidable events such as the emergence of AI and the unfolding climate crisis (“grey rhinos”) (Lyon & Popov, 2022).⁴ During the COVID-19 crisis, the ability to develop and produce a vaccine in a short timespan and at large scale, was instrumental in mitigating the pandemic to controllable levels. However, concerns about the emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies and the lack of EU power in the area have raised similar concerns about the EU’s technology dependency and ability to regulate

¹ With many thanks to Erik Canton, Julien Ravet, Florent Bernard, Niall Lawlor, Haya Al-Ajlani, Florence Benoit, Bianca Cavicchi, Nicola Dotti, Valentina Di Girolamo, Douglas Robinson, Frank Vandermeeren, and Ingrid Zegers for their contributions and comments

² The five industrial revolutions are the industrial revolution, “the age of steam and railways”, “the age of steel and heavy engineering”, “the age of oil, autos and mass production” and “the ICT revolution” (Perez 2015, p.6)

³ see, for example, (Cantner, 2023)

⁴ See also <https://blogs.cfainstitute.org/investor/2017/10/23/do-gray-rhinos-pose-a-greater-threat-than-black-swans/> Retrieved September 2024

enough to protect its citizens without stifling its own competitive edge (European Commission, Richardson, Renda, & al., 2024).⁵

The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has developed a Framework for Anticipatory Governance of Emerging Technologies emphasising the need to enhance strategic intelligence in terms of foresight and technology assessment, monitoring and evaluation, and modelling. This framework also includes a “synthesis of perspectives to coordinate across agencies for the purpose of informing governance” (2024). This is based on earlier research on this topic underlying the strategic implications of technology monitoring and assessment (Robinson, Winickoff, & Kreiling, 2023).

Both the United States (US) and the People’s Republic of China (China) implement technological and strategic policies to gain or maintain a competitive edge over other countries and regions – particularly each other – in key technologies. Continuous monitoring and assessment of their respective capabilities in an international perspective is part and parcel of both countries’ policy tool kit to design effective policies.

A major global player in the international innovation landscape, China has been carefully monitoring its technological development and emerging strengths and weaknesses since 1956. The Chinese government analysed 35 “chokepoint technologies” that are necessary for its “technology self-reliance” - similar to the concept of technology sovereignty- and has stated its intention to reorient its efforts towards overcoming the existing gaps in these specific technologies.⁶ In a similar vein, the United States government created in 1972 an Office of Technology Assessment (OTA)⁷ designed to provide advice on specific scientific issues to the US Congress and other legislators, later suppressed in 1995. Within the executive branch, the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP)⁸, was created to directly advise the US President, and staffed by specialists and researchers of the technologies assessed. It is designed to support the government with advice on the formulation and implementation of policies related to science and technology. Recent works have called for a return to the OTA to provide more consistent monitoring and assessment of technologies to a wider range of legislators and stakeholders.⁹

⁵ Graabak, Koomen, Reddel, *Five Emerging Technologies to Act On Now*, March 2024, retrieved August 2024 from : <https://icfg.eu/five-emerging-technologies-to-act-on-now-2024/>

⁶ <https://www.intelligence.senate.gov/sites/default/files/documents/os-dmurdick-051122.pdf> (retrieved September 2024) see also [China’s new scientists | Breaking China’s technological chokepoints](#) Retrieved January 2025.

⁷ <https://ota.fas.org/> retrieved November 2024

⁸ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/> retrieved November 2024

⁹ <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/it-is-time-to-restore-the-us-office-of-technology-assessment/> retrieved September 2024

Currently, the EU lacks a systemic technology monitoring function comparable to the US and China. Several key reports on the EU, notably Letta's recent report *Much More than a Market*, and Draghi's *The future of European competitiveness*¹⁰ show that Europe lags behind the US and China in certain key technologies. The reports warn that such technological lag can affect Europe's competitiveness, future prosperity, its ability to tackle societal challenges, and compromise its ability to defend itself against foreign aggression.

Therefore, to secure its future, **Europe needs to keep up with technological development, but its lack of monitoring system contributes into its lagging behind the US and China.** Both global competitors are already monitoring their technological capabilities and acting upon the information centrally, while the EU system is very fragmented even at the EU level. Suleyman & Bhaskar (2023)'s *The Coming Wave* calls for governments to acquire the in-house technical expertise to be "an equal partner in the coming wave" of disruptive technologies (part. AI). They emphasise that "[The governments'] first task should be to better monitor and understand developments in technology. Countries need to understand in detail, for example, what data their populations supply, how and where it is used, and what it means; administrations should have a strong sense of the latest research, where the frontier is, where it's going, how their country can maximise upsides" (Suleyman & Bhaskar, 2023) .

The EU needs to monitor and anticipate its position (relative strength and weakness) in emerging technologies (European Commission, Dixon-Declève, Renda, & al., 2023). The purpose of such a monitoring is manifold:

- To gauge the EU' strengths and weaknesses in terms of exploring, developing and deploying new technologies, including the transitions from research to practical application and market deployment;
- To understand other players' moves in terms of innovation policy, with a perspective on long-term security, prosperity and sustainability;
- To create awareness and consensus (among policymakers, but also across government, industry, academia, society) around where we stand in terms of the development and uptake of critical technologies;
- To build momentum and mobilise actors (society, companies, governments, academia) to seize opportunities and contribute to strengthening our technological capabilities (e.g. through research, innovation, education, investments, regulation).

¹⁰ (European Commission, 2024) and (European Commission, 2024)

With regard to the general calls concerning strategic autonomy and technology sovereignty that currently dominate the political discussions, the **EU needs a more nuanced discussion and understanding of where it stands in regard to certain critical technologies** and where it risks being left behind or becoming dependent on research, innovation and companies from other regions.

This policy brief discusses the state of play in technology monitoring and assessment (TMA) in the US, China and the EU, and how the EU could tailor such monitoring to its needs and interests. It first outlines the role of TMA in R&I and economic policy, then compares features of the EU, US and Chinese TMA systems, and concludes by outlining methodologies and features of a coherent TMA system in the European Union.

1. The added value of technology monitoring and assessment for anticipatory European policies

Strong technological capacity in strategic sectors is critical to secure Europe's competitiveness. Strengthening EU's competitive edge in global innovation markets involves addressing the gap in investment and development in key technologies. The EU's position to lead technological change in areas related to strategic productivity-enhancing technologies remains weaker than that of the US or China (European Commission, Steeman, Di Girolamo, & Mitra, 2024). This part will cover the role of TMA in EU economic and strategic competitiveness.

1.1 Anticipating competitors

Technology monitoring and assessment (TMA) is a crucial element of anticipatory technology governance. In its STI Outlook 2023, the OECD outlines a framework for informing decision makers on key technology trends, understanding stakeholders concerns and interests, and the building and steering of technological and industrial agendas (OECD, 2023). The latter can be expanded to the anticipation of systemic competitors given the strategic importance of technologies in global economic and geopolitical competition (Szczepanski, 2024).

At the policy level, TMA has a triple goal: assessing the relative position against competitors, understanding other competitors' moves, and sharing information within the policymakers and stakeholders. **As such, TMA should include data and intelligence on the positioning of global competitors** and their approaches to R&I policy and technology governance. This data will help governments understand how to change their own R&I policies in accordance with the actions of their key competitors.

A notable example of TMA is the overarching objective of the innovation and industrial strategy launched by China in 2015 “*Made in China 2025*”. This strategy aimed to break through the ceiling of low-tech and labour-intensive manufacturing by targeting specific future industries, such as robotics and next generation information technologies. China has concentrated its efforts on sectors crucial to the fourth industrial revolution, including smart manufacturing, digitalisation and emerging technologies. This focus had the clear intent of leapfrogging foreign competitors and assuming a leading position in areas where important technology gaps have emerged.¹¹ Ten years later, this jump has been partly achieved, as can be seen in Figure 1, where China leads on the top 6 most complex technologies¹². Meanwhile, the EU is in a lead position only for 6 technology areas in the area of the green transition, and places 3rd behind China and the US in the most complex technologies.

Other global players such as South Korea, the US and Japan have shown their capacity to specialise in complex technologies (European Commission, Di Girolamo, Mitra, & Ravet, 2023). The EU needs to be able to anticipate these efforts to not find itself on the backfoot when its competitors take initiative, especially given their tendency towards competitive approaches to technology policy.¹³ Future policy changes envisioned in recent US policy developments may further increase the urgency of a European TMA to circumvent technological dependencies, current and projected. Figure 1 especially underlines this as the risk of dependence of the EU to either the US or China in future digital technologies is high.

¹¹ Zenglein, M.J., Holzmann, A; *Evolving Made in China 2025: China’s industrial policy in the quest for global tech leadership*, Mercator Institute for China Studies, 2019, retrieved Aug 2024 from : <https://merics.org/en/report/evolving-made-china-2025>

¹² « Complex technologies » is a concept of technologies that are relatively rarer than other technologies in terms of specialisation per country. These technologies often require significant capacity in terms of infrastructure, knowledge and investment, as well as experience in the first place. See Figure 1 note and part 3.2.4 for more details.

¹³ Manuel, A.; Singh, P. et al.; *Compete, Contest, and Collaborate: How to Win the Technology Race with China*, “How to Win the Technology Race with China”, 2020 https://www.aspeninstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Manuel_Singh.pdf

The EU's position in complex (digital and green) technologies

2019-2022

Figure 1 - The global position of the EU in complex technologies. Source: European Commission, 2024

Note: The results are based on an analysis of patent data to understand the complexity and potential for specialization in different technology areas. On the y-axis, technologies are ranked according to how advanced or complex they are, with scores ranging between 0 (less complex) and 100 (more complex). The x-axis (showing the relatedness density) represents how easily a country can build comparative advantage in a particular technology, depending on how closely related it is to other technologies the country is already strong in. The size of the bubbles shows how much each country has already specialized in a technology, using a measure of “revealed comparative advantage” (RCA), which reflects their competitive strength in that field.

This understanding of the position can also help EU policymakers in prioritizing technologies relevant to their policy objectives. It would also allow for other levels of policymaking (national and local levels) to align with each other, thus contributing to tackle the problem of resource dispersion identified by the Draghi report (European Commission, 2024).

1.2 Explaining future innovation dynamics to current policymakers

As outlined above, technology monitoring and assessment should be integrated into broader strategic efforts focused on the objectives driving technological development. **TMA can play a role in strengthening the EU's innovation capability and its ability to anticipate economic and technological challenges by providing visible, useful outputs that can reach a non-specialist audience.** To this effect, the dedicated

Knowledge4Policy platform¹⁴ - a platform centralising scientific knowledge from knowledge services - is an attempt by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) to enable access to data and evidence. The platform is a promising effort to allow policymakers to reach data and reports, with the presence of "knowledge brokers" tasked with explaining the knowledge. However, the platform still requires the participating services to process this data and knowledge, transforming it into actionable intelligence.

Some studies suggest that **the ability of policymakers to absorb specialist information is limited** (Ouimet, 2009)¹⁵, particularly when monitoring trends of emerging technologies are targeted at specific domains (such as green technologies or healthcare) in a context where systemic policies are urgently needed to tackle policy silos (European Commission, Richardson, Renda, & al., 2024). As such, **additional efforts are required** to strengthen both the ability of policymakers to absorb the massive amounts of information necessary to understand emerging technological trends, as well as **put them in context with pertinent policy options, develop adapted solutions, and understand the potential interactions between concurrently emerging technologies** in radically different domains (Jiang & Zhao, 2019). This is where TMA can and should play a role, as technology monitoring **should be targeted at enabling policymakers to follow technology development and understand their impacts** in order to make evidence-based decisions.

1.3 The place of TMA in the policy cycle

The elaboration of European policymaking is commonly understood to follow a policy cycle rotating between policy formulation and policy evaluation and feedback. Figure 2 shows the current positioning of TMA in the policy cycle, its interactions with the steps of the policy cycle and the positioning of the current EU TMA system in it. **It shows that the TMA system is not entirely integrated within the EU policy approach**, as it is mostly used for policy inputs but is not part of any evaluation and monitoring effort, nor within the Better Regulation approach¹⁶. This means that the TMA practice cannot evolve and adapt its outputs to feed the policy formulation with requests adapted to the needs outlined during the implementation and evaluation. Chapter 2: State of Technology Monitoring expands on this issue.

The policy formulation of **non-investment legislative instruments** (European legislative instruments that do not direct investments but rather outline legal

¹⁴ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/home_en Last accessed Decembre 2024

¹⁵ See also (Saraf, Liang, & Xue, 2013) for a discussion on this question from a for-profit private sector organisation, which was useful to extrapolate the issue of capacity of absorption of information on digital technologies by an organisation.

¹⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation_en

frameworks) would benefit from TMA and use-cases developed as part of policy advice. They would mostly apply to technology governance, although the concept can have ramifications ranging from the inception to the use of these technologies, in areas as diverse as research, consumer protection and manufacturing. This includes for example regulations and directives on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI).

The policy formulation of **investment legislative instruments** (European legislative instruments outlining the use of funding such as Framework Programmes (FPs)) would benefit from TMA, but also contribute to it, especially in the parts of the FPs dedicated to advancing research in monitoring and those dedicated to policy experimentation, which would also feed into the legislative instruments. It would also serve to guide the investments in, and deployment of the technologies prioritised through TMA, from infrastructures to education. The European Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (Horizon Europe) stands to benefit from the further development of TMA in its policy formulation, monitoring and evaluation.

A coherent and centralising effect of technology monitoring is that it allows to align policies in different areas in a complementary manner: should the organisations in charge of environmental and agricultural policies base their decision on the same knowledge and impacts of technologies, their policymaking can be better aligned. This is also true regarding the evolution of technologies over time: the monitoring element of TMA enables policymakers to follow developments over time and compare the emergence of new technologies with known patterns.

Figure 2 - Positioning of TMA in the policy cycle.

Overall, policy coordination is key to ensure that the input from TMA will provide policymakers with the tools necessary for their work, but also for it to benefit from the policy inputs and the monitoring and evaluation frameworks such as the evaluation of Framework programmes.

1.4 Enabling entrepreneurship

The implementation of a coherent TMA system as part of EU and national R&I policymaking has the potential to bolster the dividends of innovation in Europe by providing crucial insights and guidance to actors along the value chain of innovation entrepreneurship.

Firstly, a TMA system can play a critical role in fostering **the capacity of policymakers and public investors to recognise early breakthrough innovation** and its potential impact, in the economic, environmental, social or defence sphere. For policymakers, access to up-to-date data and expertise on technological specificities allows for better informed decision-making, enabling them to develop relevant R&I policies able to foster a thriving entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial environment.

Secondly, such a system **enhances visibility for investors by identifying “hot investments” in emerging technologies** that have growth potential on the medium to long term. By highlighting areas of future breakthrough technological advancement and high growth potential, reports of such a system can attract investment into these promising fields, driving economic growth and encouraging further development of new ideas into new products. **An open and visible TMA system can also create a snowball effect among non-venture-capital investors**, where early investment by venture capitals can foster trust and broader interest by conservative investors who would then invest more readily and with more confidence in these emerging technologies, further fuelling innovation.

Thirdly, for innovators, companies, researchers and educators, **a monitoring system can provide an overview of emerging trends and guide them towards promising fields**. By providing a clear view of technological trends and market potential, such a system could help entrepreneurs and companies align their efforts with areas of high potential. Such natural convergence could streamline the innovation process as it gains momentum, mobilizing and focusing resources and increasing the likelihood of successful market entry.

Fourthly, **a TMA system would enable policymakers to anticipate the specific needs of innovators**, especially in non-established or nascent markets. By understanding technological implications and the challenges that innovators face, **policymakers can design funding programs, regulatory frameworks, and support measures tailored to the emerging technology**. This anticipatory approach ensures that support mechanisms are not only

available but also relevant from the onset, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of government intervention in fostering innovation.

A comprehensive European TMA system holds significant potential to help the EU bridge the lab-to-market gap. It would support entrepreneurship by providing critical insights, gathering and focusing investment, policy, and innovation efforts. It can also support the EU's goals towards open strategic autonomy by fostering a better informed and responsive entrepreneurial and policy ecosystem.

1.5 Further economic and societal impacts of TMA

The explicit objective of Technology Assessment is to assess the potential impact of technologies. As such, by informing policymakers, industries, researchers and civil society, TMA has the potential to make a large positive impact on society, by preventing misuses and supporting regulation enabling safe innovation from the onset (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 2024).

TMA also impacts research by granting visibility and a seat at the table to field experts, it contributes to the legitimacy of science and enables regulation that encourages safe innovation without stifling research.

Lastly, by providing clear and comprehensive results, TMA would contribute to the understanding of emerging technologies and the political decisions accompanying them by civil society. It would also empower civil society and industry actors to seize the knowledge developed to appropriate and use new technologies. This could lead to more technology oriented corporate STI strategies in line with the digital transition or empower companies to invest in technologies they did not feel equipped for.

2. Features of a TMA system

A TMA system needs to be embedded in the policy cycle but requires also complex governance and methodologies to provide the desired outputs. This section looks at features of TMA systems and provides tools and examples into the design of a systemic European TMA system.

2.1 Governance of TMA systems

While TMA presents significant added value, it requires **structure, resources, and expertise to ensure coherent and consistent TMA over time and across fields.**

Firstly, **TMA needs to be aligned with the goals outlined above.** A clear articulation of the steps and procedures will be necessary to determine the appropriate approaches. This alignment must be complemented with a clarity in scope, notably about the granularity of analysis, and the perspective - for example, a supply-chain or sociotechnical perspective (OECD, 2023).

Secondly, **TMA requires participation mechanisms for stakeholders with different kinds of expertise and experience,** depending on resources available (i.e., staffing and funding), scope (relevant social groups), and the time-horizon. TMA must be able to consider the social, technological, economic, environmental, political, ethical and demographic aspects of the technology emergence, development and deployment. This **discussion needs also to take into account the values, frames, and biases inherent to monitoring approaches.** Especially in the context of foresight work, different stakeholders will have their own perspectives, professional and social contexts and various biases that may shape both their opinions and reactions to others. In addition to evidence base, a discussion around biases is important to ensure trust in the TMA as a reliable source. (OECD, 2023) (2024)

Thirdly, as technology monitoring and assessment gathers data and structures disparate and unclear information, **it should maximise its usability by providing decision makers with understandable interpretations.** Robust TMA should demonstrate careful consideration of the target audience for the intelligence produced, and of this audience's absorptive capacity (OECD, 2023).

Fourth, a **TMA system needs to be nested within governance** in order to maximise its added value to policymakers. As part of the policy cycle, it can benefit from policy evaluation practices, and be an integral part of foresight exercises at the onset of strategy formulation. It needs to **be able to reach non-specialist policymakers,** especially in the context of emerging technologies or technologies with complex value chains and social, environmental and economic impacts. (2024)

Fifth, **TMA needs to be consistent over the long-term.** Understanding the evolution of the technologies and the position of the EU and its competitors will require **consistent monitoring in time** over a long period. This also means keeping a **perspective in the medium and long-term,** as the potential impact of emerging technologies is not apparent in the short term. This point is especially important in a European context, as, as we will see in Chapter 3, many initiatives in the domain are project-based and therefore limited in time.

2.2 TMA structures: Technology Observatories

Technology Observatories are organisations or departments specifically tasked with technology monitoring, and, in some instances, technology assessment. A variety of Technology Observatories are found across the world, both from government research organization and academia. However, many technology observatories are stemming from public research organisations, with a significant number being fixed-term projects.

Notable Technology observatories include:

- [The Critical Technology Observatory](#)
- [The Critical technology Tracker](#)
- [The EPO Observatory on Patents and Technology](#)
- [FORWIT – FTI Monitor](#)
- [The HCERES Science and technology observatory \(OST\)](#)
- [The Institute of Scientific and Technical Information of China \(ISTIC\)](#)
- [The SETIS Clean Energy Technology Observatory \(CETO\)](#)
- [The Technology Centre Prague](#)
- [The United Kingdom Government Office for Science](#)
- [The University of Michigan technology Assessment Project](#)

We will see in chapter 3 that the US and China have dedicated technology observatories, whereas the EU has separate departments doing TMA on their own, some called observatories (all of which are specific to a field), some not.

2.3 Approaches to TMA

TMA is crucial to monitor and assess both the impact of emerging technologies and the relative position of the players and hubs globally. As technologies emerge from long research efforts and can have impacts ranging across economic, environmental and societal consequences, TMA approaches cover a broad range, often using multiple methodologies such as foresight, surveys and patents, but also involve looking into specific issues such as adoption and future evolution. Below we discuss key approaches to implementing TMA.

Knowledge generation and diffusion

A common framework for the assessment of research and innovation as bases for knowledge generation and diffusion was developed by the OECD with the Frascati (for research)¹⁷ and Oslo (for innovation)¹⁸ manuals. In this framework, patents are the most commonly used indicators for the monitoring and assessment of emerging technologies. They allow to measure knowledge generation and diffusion (OECD, 2010) and, specific methodologies such as patent monitoring, are used by industries to monitor the R&D development of their competitors.¹⁹

Recent methodologies, such as identifying technology clusters based on patent data, allow for finer analyses of innovation patterns around specific technologies (Bergeaud & Verluise, 2024).

Complexity and relatedness

Economic complexity and relatedness metrics are another approach to implementing TMA systems. These metrics are derived from the work of Hidalgo and Hausmann, which introduced a method to investigate the complexity of individual products and countries, considering their export patterns (Hidalgo & Hausmann, 2009). The underlying idea of economic complexity is that growth, development, technological change, income inequality, spatial disparities, and resilience are the visible outcomes of hidden systemic interactions (Balland & Broekel, 2022). In addition, complex technologies have shown to typically provide countries with a higher competitive advantage than less sophisticated ones (European Commission, Di Girolamo, Mitra, & Ravet, 2023).

The complexity lens can be used to identify not only the differential abilities of European regions in given technologies, but also their potential in these technologies. That is the main empirical addition of economic complexity to TMA: it can identify regions or ecosystems that are currently not actively

¹⁷ OECD (2015), *Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>.

¹⁸ OECD/Eurostat (2018), *Oslo Manual 2018: Guidelines for Collecting, Reporting and Using Data on Innovation, 4th Edition*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264304604-en>.

¹⁹ Patent monitoring is the ongoing process of tracking and analyzing patent activities within a specific technological domain or industry. It involves systematically monitoring newly published patents, patent applications, and related developments to identify emerging trends, potential infringements, and competitive threats. For individuals and companies, patent monitoring is of paramount importance as it enables intellectual property (IP) risk anticipation and mitigation and maximizes the value of IP assets. This process enables individuals and companies to stay ahead in their industries by identifying emerging technologies and trends, assessing competition, detecting patent infringements, exploring collaboration opportunities, and enhancing strategic decision-making, thus optimizing the commercialization of innovations and maintaining a competitive edge.

developing a given technology (and therefore may not have yet acquired all the necessary capabilities), but master related know-how and, therefore, have the potential to develop the technology in the future (European Commission, 2024). This would serve strongly any attempt at monitoring emerging technologies and the state of their diffusion.

Relatedness in this context refers to the “closeness” between two sets of technologies in terms on shared technological experiences and knowledge bases between organizations. This refers to the knowledge these organisations possess about these technologies; how easily skills can transfer between both and how assets invested in one technology can be used to develop or use the other. Examples of closely related technologies include cybersecurity and artificial intelligence.

Technology adoption

In addition to technology development, the actual impact of technologies comes from their adoption, namely when it bridges the gap “from lab to market”. This is another approach that enables the assessment of a region’s competitiveness. For example, the digital gap between companies has been steadily increasing in both the EU and the US in terms of adopting advanced digital technologies (European Investment Bank, 2020). Moreover, through strong investments in climate change, the EU has kept a competitive edge over the US in terms of climate change technologies. Elements relevant for the assessment of technology adoption are enabling factors such as digital infrastructure, a dynamic innovation environment, business regulations and access to finance (European Commission, 2024).

Technology Foresight

Technology foresight involves the systematic exploration of long-term technological, social, economic, and environmental trends to identify emerging technologies and their potential implications. Foresight exercises often use combined methods such as scenario planning, Delphi surveys, and backcasting, also called road-mapping: “retracing” policy interventions from an objective to the starting situation. These activities help anticipate future developments and inform strategic planning.

Technology Forecasting

Technology forecasting uses forecasting specialists (forecasters and super-forecasters) to assess complex and interacting trends and weak signals in technological and policy areas. These trends and weak signals can then be put into perspectives to forecast the evolution of technologies and their impact in the near and far future. Recent innovations using technological solutions such as the use of Large-Language Models (LLMs) could be considered to fall under this category (Vesnić Alujević, Farinha, & Pólvora, 2023).

Planning

Planning approaches based on scenario or road-mapping can help identify technologies aligned with policy objectives and that warrant investment due to

their anticipated social, economic or environmental advantages (Vesnić Alujević, Farinha, & Pólvora, 2023). These approaches are therefore more useful in conjunction with other methods to assess what technologies would be more useful to invest in depending on the needs of the future. An example of this approach could be seen as the development of the French nuclear power to answer to a dual need of military and energy sovereignty.

Innovation System Analysis

Innovation system analysis examines the complex interactions between various actors, institutions, and policies that drive the development and diffusion of new technologies. This approach helps policymakers understand the strengths and weaknesses of their innovation ecosystems and identify areas where policy interventions may be needed to support technology development and adoption.

Stakeholder consultations

Public-private partnerships, stakeholder surveys involve collaboration between governments, businesses, research institutions, and other stakeholders to promote the development and diffusion of new technologies. These partnerships can support TMA by pooling resources, sharing knowledge and expertise, and coordinating actions to address common challenges.

Expert surveys

As cutting-edge domains often involve researchers in a very small community of practice within a field, field experts are useful to survey to complement systematic data analysis. For example, Delphi surveys and (super)forecasts (Karwetski, 2021) help to map technological developments and trends for later sense-making in scenarios and associated foresight activities.

Early-warning systems

Domain specific interactions of technological systems with their ecosystem (developers, producers and users) can also contribute to the monitoring of technologies and technological needs. For example, early-warning systems hospital reporting for pathogens such as the Nucleic Acid Observatory can enable to detect new biological threats and design new disease surveillance methods, which in turn can help steer the development of medical technologies designated to combat them²⁰. As catastrophes have proven to be extreme catalysts for human technological advancements, domains such as natural- and man-made disaster monitoring and early warning mechanisms can prove promising in monitoring technologies that may become relevant as dangers arise.

²⁰ <https://naobservatory.org/> retrieved November 2024

System Dynamics

System dynamics provides a framework for understanding how new technologies develop and spread within their wider socio-technical context, involving industry actors, regulatory bodies, end users and policy goals. By simulating how key elements - such as the accumulation of resources (for example, the number of installations or the pool of skilled workers), the flow of investments and information, and the ways these elements interact over time to either amplify or dampen progress – using real-world data, it becomes possible to monitor real-world indicators (like patent filings, funding patterns and uptake rates) against expected trends, thereby estimating future trends and development pathways. In addition, adjusting critical inputs – e.g., research budgets, regulatory milestones or supply-chain constraints - enables “what-if” scenario simulations to evaluate effects of different policy options, forecast when a technology is likely to reach maturity, and pinpoint the most effective points of intervention. Existing system dynamics models in areas such as renewable energy and health technologies already demonstrate this approach, but they require a thorough update - integrating more timely data feeds and a modular structure - before they can support comprehensive, real-time monitoring and assessment at scale (Ginters, Barkane, & Vincent, 2010), (Djanatljev, Kolominsky-Rabas, Hofmann, Aisenbrey, & German, 2014), and (European Commission, 2025).

Technology Assessment methodologies

TMA has already benefitted from a certain amount of literature such as the OECD framework for Technology Assessment. The framework outlines best practices in TMA such as the Novel and Exceptional Technology and Research Advisory Committee (NEXTRAC) developed in the US National Institutes of Health (Robinson, Winickoff, & Kreiling, 2023) p.13). Furthermore, the US National Science Foundation has developed a programme of assessment of technology outcomes of emerging technologies (the APTO programme), to develop models able to predict future as well as past states of technology outcomes in technology capabilities, production and use. Some EU Member States have also developed their own approaches to TA and use them for their own National R&I strategies, such as the Netherlands²¹.

²¹ See the methodology used by the Dutch administration here : <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/rapporten/2023/12/31/quantitative-analysis-of-dutch-research-and-innovation-on-key-technologies> (Retrieved December 2024)

3. Current State of Technology monitoring

While there are common features of TMA systems, the shape of such systems is also dependent on the context of their emergence, and the goals pursued through them. In this section, we will look at the different approaches taken to TMA of the EU, the US and China as examples of the paradigms followed by each administration.

3.1 The US approach to technology monitoring and assessment: Distributed knowledge, Centralised decision

Technology assessment at the policy level has been a staple of US policymaking since the 1970s.²²

On the legislative side, the Office of Technology Assessment (OTA) advised the US Congress between 1972 and 1995, with a lasting legacy.²³ However, the US Congress, which is equivalent to the European Parliament but divided in two chambers, has a Science, Space and Technology Committee²⁴, that has been reviled for being understaffed and with a lack of expertise.²⁵ The main expertise needs of the Congress have been fulfilled by the Government Accountability Office (GAO) who has been handling the TA needs of the Congress since the discontinuation of the OTA with the Science, technology Assessment and Analytics (STAA) team²⁶. The STAA cooperates with the agencies and state departments (ministries) in order to base its monitoring and assessments on the best available evidence.

In the White House, the US executive branch, the National Science and Technology Council (NSTC) is “the principal means by which the Executive Branch coordinates science and technology policy across the diverse entities

²² It must be noted that this report was being finalised during the waning hours of the Biden Presidency. As such, the system does take into account any changes taking place after the 31st December 2024, and little extrapolation can be made at the time of writing regarding the changes projected by the Trump presidency.

²³ Federation of American Scientists, « *Technology Assessment and Congress* », https://ota.fas.org/technology_assessment_and_congress/ retrieved December 2024

²⁴ <https://www.congress.gov/committee/house-science-space-and-technology/hssy00> See the website of the committee: <https://science.house.gov/> Accessed January 2025

²⁵ See <https://www.brennancenter.org/our-work/analysis-opinion/science-poor-congress-needs-more-google-searches-tech-legislation> and the recommendations here <https://www.belfercenter.org/publication/building-21st-century-congress-improving-congress-science-and-technology-expertise> Accessed January 2025

²⁶ <https://www.gao.gov/about/careers/our-teams/STAA> Accessed January 2025

It must be noted that the GAO is at the origin of the well-known Technology Assessment Design Handbook, which itself influenced the OECD Technology assessment for emerging technologies. The TA Design Handbook can be found here:

<https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-21-347g> (Retrieved January 2025)

that make up the Federal research and development enterprise.”²⁷ It works in tandem with the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) spearheaded by the Chief Technology officer (CTO) directly attached to the president of the US, which it advises and for whom it develops its science and technology policy.²⁸ These bodies are completed by the President’s Council of Advisors on Science and Technology (PCAST): an advisory group composed of scientists, engineers from academia and industry alike.²⁹

This has led the Department of State³⁰ to launch the Office of the Special Envoy for Critical & Emerging Technologies, in order to monitor critical technologies and ensure the US access to these technologies.³¹ It completes the Office of Critical Technology Protection, active in the domain of technology sovereignty for the United States³², and the Department of Defence Trade Control.³³ The national Science Foundation (USNSF) also plays an active role in aligning science and technology research with US competitiveness via the APTO programme, centred around developing models for assessment of technology outcomes of emerging technologies.³⁴

Through the National Science Foundation, a National Network for Critical Technology Assessment³⁵ was founded “to pilot analytical approaches to assessing technology maturity, trajectories and impact that can drive development of data-driven options for future government investments.”³⁶ This has led to a landmark report on a framework for critical technology assessment.³⁷ Main findings from the report include:

²⁷ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Critical-and-Emerging-Technologies-List-2024-Update.pdf> retrieved January 2025

²⁸ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/> Accessed October 2024

²⁹ <https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/administration/eop/ostp/pcast/about> Accessed January 2025. It is at the time of writing unclear whether the new President of the US will appoint a PCAST, as it is a purely advisory body which, while it yields a great influence as a contact point between government, academia and industry at the highest level, does not have powers.

³⁰ The equivalent of the EU Foreign Secretary, or the Foreign Minister’s office in a national government, but with powers over immigration policy as well

³¹ <https://www.state.gov/bureaus-offices/secretary-of-state/office-of-the-special-envoy-for-critical-and-emerging-technology/> Accessed September 2024

³² <https://www.state.gov/bureaus-offices/secretary-of-state/office-of-the-special-envoy-for-critical-and-emerging-technology/> Accessed September 2024

³³ <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2025-01-17/html/2025-01313.htm> Retrieved January 2025

³⁴ <https://new.nsf.gov/funding/opportunities/assessing-predicting-technology-outcomes-apt0> Accessed October 2024

³⁵ <https://nncta.org/> Accessed January 2025

³⁶ <https://new.nsf.gov/news/new-report-identifies-pathways-strengthen-us>

³⁷ <https://nncta.org/files/documents/nncta-final-report.pdf> Accessed January 2024

- The importance of competitiveness relative to China and new metrics to measure it in the domain of disruptive innovation and emerging technologies;
- The importance of using a supply-chain approach to analysing vulnerability in a technological domain;
- To design a “rapid Critical Technology Assessment function” for both the US Congress and the executive branch to function as “an ‘analytic ARPA’, marshalling the country’s rich analytic capacity across disciplines and institutions to link technology investments and policy to the country’s multiple missions.”³⁸

A tentative positioning of this recommendation has been placed in the US TMA system reconstructed in Figure 3.

This deployment of TMA builds on a consistent approach to technology leadership based on common shared principles in the US, the main one being the creation of market value. As such, US government departments and agencies are geared towards enabling US companies to acquire technologies from partners and competitors across the world. Several agencies also updated their approach based on lessons learned from the practice of technological development; the often discussed “Advanced research Projects Agency” structure, which originated in the defence agency DARPA has been emulated in health (ARPA-H), energy (ARPA-E) and infrastructure (ARPA-I).

These departments and agencies lead TMA in their own areas. The Department of Commerce for example, is active in this domain with the US Patent and Trademark Office Patent Technology Monitoring Team³⁹ and the Bureau of Industry and Security.⁴⁰ The Department of Defence has the, DARPA, the Defence Innovation Unit, tasked with collecting civilian innovations with defence potential⁴¹, and the Defence Technology Security Administration⁴². The latter one can be noted for its role in technology transfer in the US administration, in collaboration with the Department of State and the Department of Commerce.⁴³ In addition to their roles as advisors to the President, the NSTC and the OSTP are also actively leading in the development of public-private cooperation at a large scale, via the BRAIN

³⁸ <https://nncta.org/files/documents/nncta-one-page-summary.pdf> retrieved 03/12/2024

³⁹ <https://www.uspto.gov/learning-and-resources/electronic-data-products/patent-technology-monitoring-team-ptmt-patent> Accessed September 2024

⁴⁰ <https://www.bis.doc.gov/index.php/other-areas/office-of-technology-evaluation-ote/technology-assessments> Accessed October 2024

⁴¹ <http://diu.mil/> Accessed January 2025

⁴² <https://www.dtsa.mil/SitePages/default.aspx> Accessed January 2025

⁴³ See the 2021 Technology Transfer Control plan guidelines <https://www.dtsa.mil/SitePages/about-dtsa/directorates/export-control/TTCP-Guidelines-v4.3.pdf> retrieved January 2025

initiative⁴⁴, a partnership between public and private actors with a common goal of accelerating the development of innovative neurotechnologies. This project was developed under President Obama by the OSTP, and successfully involved DARPA and the NSF, but also companies and universities across the US and abroad. Under the Biden administration, the CHIPS and Science Act⁴⁵ introduced legislation charging the OSTP with formulating a National Standards Strategy For Critical And Emerging Technologies, although it is unclear whether these structures will be maintained under the current administration.⁴⁶

US R&I policy is also somewhat determined at the state level in the US⁴⁷, with states contributing budgets which vary greatly depending on their capacities, However, state governments spent in R&D approximately \$3bn in 2023.⁴⁸ This amount seems negligible in comparison with a proposed federal budget spending of approximately \$202 billion for 2025.⁴⁹ Furthermore, analysis of the TMA capacities at the state level and the coordination between the federal and the state level in R&I policy fall outside of the scope of this paper.

⁴⁴ <https://braininitiative.nih.gov/about/overview> Accessed January 2025

⁴⁵ <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/PLAW-117publ167/html/PLAW-117publ167.htm>

⁴⁶ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2024/07/26/fact-sheet-implementing-the-national-standards-strategy-for-critical-and-emerging-technology/>
Accessed January 2025

⁴⁷ <https://www.dwih-newyork.org/en/research-innovation/the-research-and-innovation-landscape-in-the-usa/research-and-innovation-policy/> accessed December 2024

⁴⁸ <https://nces.nsf.gov/pubs/nsf25308> accessed January 2025

⁴⁹ <https://crsreports.congress.gov/product/pdf/R/R48307/1> accessed January 2025

Figure 3 - U.S. TMA system. In orange federal departments. In grey is a tentative positioning of the recommendation from the NSF to create a "rapid assessment capacity" capable of informing both the executive (orange) and legislative (green) branches. Note the distribution of innovation-based technology monitoring with the "ARPA-style" agencies in other departments, and the link of the GAO to the agencies it audits and cooperates with. Source: authors' own work.

3.2 Chinese TMA: A system at the core of Chinese economic and defence policy since 1956

Since the 19th century, the Chinese government had an active policy of technology transfer from the West.⁵⁰ Critical technologies for defence and economic development were identified and brought in via foreign deployment of know-how and joint ventures (Brown S. R., 1979). An example of these programmes, based on a list of critical technologies, is the 863 Programme, launched in 1986, to « monitor the high-tech trends in the world and make efforts to develop China's own high-tech industries. » (Sun & Cao, 2023). Shortly after the accession of the CCP to power, a world-class open-source document procurement and analysis system dedicated to advances in foreign technology was established to support the development of Chinese industry and economy (Hannas & Chang, 2021). From 1949 to 1980, the number of universities in China tripled, and tripled again until 2006 (Jian, 2008).

⁵⁰ Most of the substance of this chapter originates from the excellent book by Sun and Cao "The Political Economy of Science, Technology, and Innovation in China: Policymaking, Funding, Talent, and Organization" (Sun & Cao, 2023) and the precise study by Hannas and Chang titled: "China's STI Operations; Monitoring foreign science and technology through open sources" (Hannas & Chang, 2021).

The paucity of publicly available sources in English makes it difficult to establish a clear and up-to-date picture of the Chinese TMA system. It is surmised to be extensive, comprising at least 100 000 officials and researchers, providing extensive networks of collaboration across government and private organisations and leading a consistent professionalization programme, including formations (Hannas & Chang, 2021).

In this context, two features need to be considered to understand the TMA apparatus in the Chinese bureaucratic system: the first one is that of the concept of “two names, one institution”: the administration of the People’s Republic of China is centred around the Chinese Communist Party (CCP), which acts as a sort of “parallel state” doubling high-level official government institutions. For example, the Central Science and Technology Commission (CSTC) is legally distinct from the CCP Commission of the same name but is staffed by the same experts with the same organisational structure (Sun & Cao, 2023). In this context, the reporting of the Ministry of Science and Technology (MOST, officially the government) reports to the CSTC (which is both a government body and a CCP structure).

A second element is the fact that decision-making regarding specific policy approaches have been until 2023 led by the MOST, but subject to “inter-group” negotiations at the highest level (Sun & Cao, 2023). The creation of the CSTC in 2023 was with the objective of integrating the current functions related to science, technology, and innovation policymaking in the MOST, the National Development and Reform Committee (NDRC, responsible for the 5-Year Plan), the Ministry of Industry and Information Technologies (MOIT), and other agencies. « Similar to the White House OSTP in the USA and the Office for Science and Technology Strategy in the UK, China’s OSTP is to maximize the role of S&T in advancing health, agriculture, national security, environmental protection, and other domains for the country. » (Sun & Cao, 2023). As such, **the TMA system we are assessing is the product of a recent reform endeavouring to improve the Chinese harnessing of emerging technologies in attaining policy goals.**

The Chinese technology monitoring, assessment and transfer system has a proven track record, as it is held partly responsible for the incredible Chinese economic advances throughout the 20th and the first quarter of the 21st century (Jian, 2008). It supported China’s development of nuclear and other strategic weapons. Its paramount role persists today, with marked improvements with the advances of science (Huang, Mei, Liao, & Zhao, 2024).

The Chinese TMA appears to be strongly oriented towards technology monitoring, assessment and transfer (Brown & Singh, 2020), with extensive efforts placed into its implementation and daily execution, and an emphasis on metrics and “customer” interaction (Hannas & Chang, 2021). This ‘customer’ interaction should be understood in the sense of the use of data and briefings

by policymakers and its use in policy in general. This is further reinforced by more than a dozen journals supporting the Chinese TMA enterprise, as well as social organizations at the national and local levels. The apparatus is staffed by experts in all relevant disciplines, attesting to its thorough professionalization, and covers every possible discipline (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Structure of the Chinese TMA system. The National Science and Technology Library (NSTL) is directly connected to the Ministry of Science and Technology (MOST) and reports to the three CCP Commissions responsible for S&T, Defence and the 5-Year Plans. Source: author's own work, constructed from (Hannas & Chang, 2021) and (Sun & Cao, 2023)

This emphasis on transfer and extensive professionalization and distribution across the different levels of government are two main differences between the Chinese and Western (US or EU) TMA systems: China *transfers* technology through a vast apparatus across the government (Brown S. R., 1979), *including regional governments* while US state-level and EU national TMA efforts are specific to the states/Member States and relatively uncoordinated with the supranational level.

Furthermore, the Chinese TMA apparatus possesses a clear connection to defence research and strategic intelligence, similarly to the US TMA apparatus. This connection is however different from the one present in the US as the latter DoD is integrated in the executive branch's general approach to TMA, with civilian research directly contributing to US defence TMA. By contrast, the Chinese approach has two separate streams of TMA, with Figure 5 outlining a broad structure of Chinese defence TMA as explained by (Hannas & Chang, 2021). It must be noted that these are extrapolations from secondary sources and may only be a partial picture of the Chinese defence TMA.

Figure 5 - Mission articulation of the defence part of the Chinese STI system. Note the different levels of articulation of the intelligence source, drawing from local and industry levels as well as the defence apparatus. Constructed from (Hannas & Cheung, 2021) and (Sun & Cao, 2023)

3.3 EU efforts: An ecosystem fragmented at the analytical and the policy levels

The EU's efforts towards anticipatory governance in emerging technologies have been extremely diverse both in terms of methodology and in terms of stakeholders involved. Figure 6 outlines the structures involved in TMA at the European level.

The European Parliament (EP) uses the Panel for the future of Science and Technology (STOA) composed of MEPs to conduct technology assessment and foresight, supported by the EP Research Service (EPRS) Scientific Foresight unit.⁵¹ Furthermore, the European parliamentary technology assessment (EPTA) network gives advice to their member states parliaments on topical issues such as nanotechnology, brain research, mobility pricing, or future energy systems.⁵² Their projects use various methods and draw on insights from citizen panels, stakeholders, workshops as well as experts in the relevant fields. The Parliament also provides the secretariat for the European Strategy and Policy Analysis System (ESPAS), an ongoing interinstitutional network across the European institutions (but not involving the Member States), performing regular horizon scanning.⁵³

⁵¹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/stoa/en/home/highlights> Accessed December 2024

⁵² <https://eptanetwork.org/> Accessed December 2024

⁵³ <https://espas.eu/about.html#HistoryAndStateOfPlay> Accessed October 2024

The European Commission (EC) has a Strategic Foresight Network (SFN) tasked with producing an annual Strategic Foresight report and coordinating the inputs from national Foresight networks.⁵⁴ The European Political Strategy Centre (EPSC), discontinued in 2022, was the European Commission's in-house think tank, aiming to engage in foresight and anticipatory governance⁵⁵, spearheading the European Commission's involvement in ESPAS. Additionally, as part of the Scientific Advice Mechanism (SAM), the group of Chief Scientific Advisors provides scientific opinions and advice to the Commission on usually complex interdisciplinary questions. The advice is based on the review and synthesis of scientific evidence by the consortium of academy networks (SAPEA).⁵⁶

The European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) is strongly involved in TMA efforts such as ESPAS and the SFN and is also involved in other activities such as text mining and trend analysis, with the Technology and Innovation Monitoring (TIM) tool⁵⁷. The JRC has also setup monitoring efforts on specific domains such as the AI Watch.⁵⁸ Other adjacent monitoring efforts are ongoing such as the European Monitor of Industrial Ecosystems (EMI) tool by the Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs (GROW).⁵⁹ The European Innovation Council (EIC) was established under the EU Horizon Europe programme coordinated by DG Research and Innovation (R&I).⁶⁰ Its objective is to support game changing innovations throughout the lifecycle from early stage research, to proof of concept, technology transfer, and the financing and scale up of start-ups and SMEs. It counts the EIC Forum as a unique feature enabling the uptake of stakeholder inputs into policies.⁶¹ Its activities include the anticipation and monitoring of emerging technologies and breakthrough innovations, but whose implementation is within the remit of the JRC through an administrative agreement.⁶² The European Research Council (ERC) as part of its activity also monitors the innovations it supports and assesses its potential for scientific

⁵⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/strategic-planning/strategic-foresight_en
Accessed November 2024

⁵⁵ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/organisation/epsc-european-political-strategy-centre_en Accessed September 2024

⁵⁶ <https://scientificadvice.eu/> Accessed October 2024

⁵⁷ <http://www.timanalytics.eu/> Accessed October 2024. For more information, see https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/text-mining/topic/tim_analytics_en

⁵⁸ <https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/id-0130> Accessed October 2024

⁵⁹ <https://monitor-industrial-ecosystems.ec.europa.eu/about/what-is-emi> Accessed November 2024

⁶⁰ https://eic.ec.europa.eu/about-european-innovation-council_en Accessed November 2024

⁶¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/building-european-innovation-ecosystem/eic-forum>
Accessed November 2024

⁶² https://eic.ec.europa.eu/document/download/d801a0d8-492e-4510-9dd6-8d942756e7c7_en?filename=EIC-workprogramme-2024.pdf Accessed December 2024

development.⁶³ The DG R&I is also responsible for the Scientific Advice Mechanism, and does also technology research and foresight through its Common Strategy & Foresight Service (CSFS) unit.⁶⁴

The Critical Technologies Observatory (CTO) was set up by the Commission in line with the Action Plan on synergies. The CTO identifies, monitors and assesses critical technologies for the space, defence and related civil sectors, their potential application and related value and supply chains. It also monitors and analyses existing and predictable technology gaps, root causes of strategic dependencies and vulnerabilities. The Commission, based on data of the CTO, presents a classified report on critical technologies and risks associated with strategic dependencies affecting security, space and defence to Member States every two years. In addition, the Commission prepares technology roadmaps based on these reports, which include mitigating measures to boost research and innovation, and reduce strategic dependencies affecting security and defence.⁶⁵ The CTO relies for a large part on the expertise of the JRC and DG DEFIS to develop its methods and analyses, and is limited in the areas of technologies it can assess.

In this line, the European Commission has also compiled a list of critical technology areas for the EU's economic security in 2023.⁶⁶ This assessment reviewed technology areas for their transformative nature and risks for peace and security but did not identify them as tools for future challenges and projects of the European Union. The Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP) was later created with the intend to boost the manufacturing of critical technologies for the green and digital transitions, as well as biotechnologies.⁶⁷ It is however only a funding facility dedicated to enable the re-deployment of funds across EU programmes towards the manufacturing of these three classes of technologies. However, its portfolio approach makes it difficult to monitor the evolution of these technologies, as the main monitoring frameworks for each project will be the ones of the funds their funding originates from (such as Cohesion policy or Horizon Europe).

The European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) routinely monitors technologies for their potential impact on privacy and data protection, with the help of the JRC.⁶⁸

⁶³ <https://erc.europa.eu/homepage> Accessed December 2024

⁶⁴ See https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/foresight_en Accessed January 2025

⁶⁵ <https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/i9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vlqhmp8tptzd?ctx=vq9pjpw5wsz1>

⁶⁶ https://defence-industry-space.ec.europa.eu/commission-recommendation-03-october-2023-critical-technology-areas-eus-economic-security-further_en Accessed August 2024

⁶⁷ https://strategic-technologies.europa.eu/index_en Accessed September 2024

⁶⁸ https://www.edps.europa.eu/data-protection/technology-monitoring_en

Furthermore, the EU through its research programmes has been developing a host of other independent initiatives and projects in TMA and foresight.⁶⁹ However, while these projects often provided substantial evidence, they were rarely part of long-term institutional efforts. Instead, they provide “background knowledge” for specific policy areas, such as the Advanced Technologies for Industry project ended in 2021.⁷⁰

Figure 2 and Figure 6 show that **there are no specific circuits dedicated to the dissemination of information** within the European Commission to enable policymakers to access resources and data besides the internal libraries. Most consultations on a specific topic go through matrixes that involve DGs on a case-by-case basis, while the official system of ISCs requires a central allocation system within each directorate. While there is a profusion of informal approaches (in-house social media, communication tools and personal networks), the fact that there is no approach to the dissemination of information across the institution can make interdisciplinary research and monitoring endeavours such as TMA complex.

As a whole, **technology monitoring and assessment initiatives within the European Commission are fragmented and inconsistent over the long term.** TMA requires a coherent and constant effort, especially for new knowledge to be incorporated into policy and organisational practice in a timely and distributed manner.

⁶⁹ Some examples include the RIBRI technology scan (<https://www.isi.fraunhofer.de/en/competence-enter/foresight/projekte/ribri.html>), and the “Anticipation and monitoring of emerging technologies and disruptive innovation” (ANTICIPINNOV) project, a collaboration between the European Commission Joint Research Centre with the European Innovation Council (EIC).

Emerging technologies: Farinha, J., Vesnic Alujevic, L., Alvarenga, A. and Polvora, A., Everybody is looking into the Future! A literature review of reports on emerging technologies and disruptive innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2023, doi:10.2760/144730, JRC134319.

⁷⁰ European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, Izsak, K., Carosella, G., Kroll, H. et al., Advanced technologies for industry – Final report – Report on technology trends and technology adoption, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/321124>

For a contextual presentation of the ATI result see <https://www.technopolis-group.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/ATI-slideshow-March-31.pdf>

Figure 6- European TMA system. orange: government-level TMA, green: parliamentary TMA, red: international organisations, blue: European Commission. Simple arrows mark inputs, double arrows mark mutual inputs or coordination. Source: authors' own work.

3.4 Challenges to technology monitoring and assessment in the EU

From the discussion above, it appears that two types of challenges impact the current landscape for TMA in the EU: structural and methodological challenges.

3.1.4 Structural challenges

Firstly, and **contrary to its US and Chinese counterparts, the EU TMA system is almost entirely disconnected from its defence and procurement area.** Only the CTO through DG DEFIS is connected to the area of defence, and focuses on supply chain risks of specific technologies, with its reports only accessible to Member States governments. A similar amount of coordination is taking place with other services.

Secondly, **the audience of TMA in the European system is at the working or middle manager (hierarchical) level.** While the Chinese system has many working-level links between its TMA and its policymaking, it does advise a high-level body (the Central Military Commission). The US TMA system is also

directly in contact with the President. In the EU however, the main links to higher policy levels are through the Secretariat-General's Strategic Foresight Network and the DG R&I Scientific Advice Mechanism and, to a lesser extent, the STOA and ESPAS. This greatly limits the overall visibility of EU higher policy levels on technology issues.

Thirdly, **a monitoring system needs to work in the long term, that is, to be capable of monitoring the evolution of technologies and technology policies over time.** This is to enable the exploration of trends and understand the degree of maturity of a field or a technology and its potential impacts. However, this requirement **increases the development and maintenance costs of such a system.** Establishing a comprehensive system that can effectively monitor a wide range of technologies requires significant financial investment in expertise either in-house or as consultants. Furthermore, the operation expenses for maintaining, updating, and securing the data and ensuring dissemination further exacerbate these costs.

Fourthly, **ensuring the usability of the EU TMA system to policymakers is another significant hurdle.** For it to be effective, it must be actively utilised by policymakers, researchers, and innovators. This requires not only raising awareness of the system's existence but also demonstrating its practical value, by reforming the European TMA system to ensure its ease of use for policymakers and its ability to deliver actionable results. Fortunately, examples abound of excellent examples of visualisations for TMA such as the FTI Monitor⁷¹, helpful to understand the relationships between technologies and technology areas, and the Radical Innovation Breakthrough Inquirer (RIBRI)⁷² visualization enabling a clear selection and prioritization of technologies based on their maturity.

Fifthly, **balancing open access to information with the need for confidentiality is a complex issue.** It is important to balance transparency, which is essential for public trust and the legitimacy of the monitoring system, with the necessity to maintain the secrecy of sensitive data. For example, data with national security implications and cutting-edge technological innovations with high potential market value must be protected. A thorough reflection on the criteria to release certain information publicly as opposed to keep it confidential could help tackle this challenge, notably by considering security concerns, intellectual property and transparency.

Lastly, **the question of the institutional structure of such TMA system would depend on its goals, its intended audience and the available budgets.** Would it be based on recurring projects, or a long-running

⁷¹ <https://fti-monitor.forwit.at/O/system> Accessed September 2024

⁷² <https://ribri.isi-project.eu/> Accessed January 2025

independent organization? Would it be the fruit of interinstitutional cooperation or is it better to maintain expertise within each policymaking body?

These limitations **highlight the need for careful planning, ongoing evaluation, and the establishment of robust monitoring and feedback frameworks to ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of TMA efforts.** In the framework of the European Commission for example, the knowledge building on the Knowledge4Policy platform⁷³ is a platform centralising TMA effort across the organisation in a free and open manner, but whose use by policymakers remains insufficiently assessed. Tools along the line of information mapping within an organisation as developed for information systems and digital technologies could offer potential for improvement into a more evidence-based approach to information dissemination (Mazur & Pec, 2021).

This means that **the fitness-for-purpose of technology monitoring and assessment to policy goals is a key challenge.** The importance and complexity of TMA for strategic policy in areas as diverse as R&I, Industrial, economic and security policies make the data collection and analysis efforts need a clear focus.

3.2.4 *Methodological challenges*

The lack of relevant data and evidence presents a first challenge to a TMA system. Monitoring efforts rely on the collection and analysis of vast amounts of data from diverse sources, necessitating a thorough quality check of this data to deem its reliability, and unbiasedness. However, achieving this level of objectivity is difficult, particularly when data sources may vary in quality, and stakeholders might seek to influence the monitor's outputs.

Methodologically, the broad diversity in TMA approaches in the EU institutions might require **the combination and use of different but complementary approaches.**

The prevalence in use of patents as a monitoring tool may lead to distortions. Patents are known to have some limitations, including:

- The time lag between patent filing and publication,

⁷³ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/home_en Accessed January 2025

- The fact that not all innovations are patented, especially in innovation ecosystems that are not very strong in enforcing intellectual property (IP)⁷⁴,
- The presence of geographical and sectoral differences in patent filings,
- The fact that many industries do not patent,
- That patents may not be relevant in some innovation processes,
- The difficulty in assessing patent quality as opposed to quantity, especially in the case of strategic patenting (I.e. where a company files numerous patents to create IP barriers against competitors), these are the main bottlenecks to be addressed.
- The lack of articulation of patents with other metrics and signals into a structural business intelligence framework

More issues and proposed solutions on the limitations of patents can be found in the literature (Grzegorzcyk & Głowiński, 2016), (Comai, 2018) (Saheb, 2020).

TMA should therefore go beyond research outputs and metrics and consider the framework conditions for such technologies to be applied, such as for example demand side and manufacturing capabilities. Exploring novel methodologies such as complexity, system dynamics and technology uptake is necessary also to provide deeper perspectives both on the socioeconomic and environmental challenges that new technologies may pose and on novel perspectives for policy action.

In addition, emerging technologies become obsolete or evolve into their maturity over time, raising the need for a regular, sustained monitoring effort in the long-term. This could not only allow to monitor the evolution of technology and assess its status but could also support the understanding of broader patterns of innovation emergence.

Lastly, **the question of how to approach the dissemination to higher levels of policymaking**. TMA has for goal to inform policy priority setting and support the elaboration and evaluation of strategy to achieve policy goals. As such, it begs the question of what kind of results are expected, and how to present these results to the intended audience. Box 1 below presents an attempt at answering the question through the approach named “Requirements engineering” (2024).

⁷⁴ See for example the discussion here <https://www.promarket.org/2021/03/19/patents-bad-measure-innovation-new-metric/> Retrieved February 2025

Answering clearly the question: Requirements engineering for TMA tools (Commission & Mazak-Huemer, 2024)

Current innovation ranking systems, such as the European Innovation Scoreboard and the Global Innovation Index, rely on composite indicators that, while simplify communication, often obscure the underlying drivers of performance and limit deeper systemic analysis. Challenges include data overload, limited open access, and tools restricted to specific purposes. To address these shortcomings, a new flexible and interactive web-based monitoring tool is required. This tool should be built on a three-tier software architecture to analyze the strengths and weaknesses technological systems, explore systemic interdependencies, and enable international comparisons, thereby enhancing the understanding of innovation dynamics.

The approach known as Requirements Engineering adopts a three-tier architecture to ensure scalability, flexibility, and usability in a technology monitoring system. At the first layer (**Data Tier**, monitoring level of the approach) data for technologies is gathered and harmonized and consolidated to promote interoperability and enable analysis.

The second layer (**Business Tier**, assessment level of the approach) is where the data is processed to identify trends and generate actionable insights for evaluating policies and predicting future developments. It should also allow for management of data sources, analytics, and user permissions, with the objective to reduce system maintenance requirements and supports the integration of new data sources and formats.

At the third layer (highest level), the **Presentation Tier** comprises a Dashboard Module that visualizes complex data through intuitive, interactive dashboards with features such as filtering and drill-downs. It generates tailored reports, enables data export, and fosters collaboration, transparency, and data-driven decision-making. Additionally, a Notification System alerts stakeholders to critical developments or opportunities, enhancing responsiveness and proactive risk management.

A prototype implementation of such an architecture is exemplified by the Austrian RTI (Research, Technology, Innovation) Monitor, accessible at <https://fti-monitor.forwit.at/O/system>. The Austrian RTI Monitor's modular design supports flexibility and scalability to meet evolving requirements, incorporate new data sources, and adapt to changing policy needs. Its high data quality and interoperability enhance the reliability of insights, while user-centric visualization and notification features ensure accessibility and actionable outputs.

This structure fosters transparency, accountability, and evidence-based decision-making, making it a robust tool for the continuous monitoring and refinement of RTI policies. Furthermore, the FTI Monitor evaluates performance through a strengths and weaknesses analysis. In doing so, it compares Austria's performance to that of the Innovation Leaders, the top three countries in each respective area, and the EU average.

4. Conclusions

In the rapidly evolving landscape of technological innovation, policymakers are scrambling to react to new developments in the face of unprecedented crises. **To maintain a competitive edge in such a dynamic environment, the EU must seek effective monitoring and anticipatory governance to ensure timely policy responses.**

TMA plays a central role in enabling governments to respond swiftly to crises and rapid shifts in the global technological landscape. **This key role has been acknowledged by the EU's global competitors.**

The US intent on maintaining its technological leadership, while China is increasing its ability to harness its domestic research while maintaining a pressure to absorb as much foreign technology as possible. Both have also shown concern regarding their analytical and methodological capabilities in TMA and have taken steps to reinforce it.

Both the US and China have also shown a **clear link between defence and civilian research and innovation**, either by integrating their TMA system with defence and the economy (US) or by creating a parallel stream with a shared knowledge base (China). This link remains missing when examining the EU TMA initiatives.

A European TMA system is also an opportunity for European defence and should help integrate it with other policy areas. The Chinese and US defence and industrial sectors have benefitted from mutual relationships of which governmental use of TMA for priority setting has been key. The EU could take inspiration from these practices in developing a TMA system that designed to support EU economic and research security.

At the EU level, numerous competing initiatives have been put forward to track trends in technology development, **highlighting the importance of a coordinated, centralised and clearly defined effort of TMA in anticipating future developments.** The coordination between EU and Member State level in TMA and strategic technology prioritisation also shows clear room for improvement, especially to support technology adoption and share best practices.

However, the EU's prevalent reliance on patents as a primary source of information in TMA frameworks is limiting. While patents are a valuable indicator of innovation, they do not capture the full spectrum of technological advancements, and often overlook the nuanced interplay of development and deployment stages. To address these limitations, it is essential to employ other perspectives. **Complexity and relatedness measures provide a more dynamic and contextual understanding** of how technologies can be developed and scaled within specific regions, including these regions'

comparative advantages in these areas. In parallel, **considering the mechanisms at the basis of the adoption of new technologies** after their development is crucial to create a clear picture of their impact.

Achieving a comprehensive and early mapping of technological trends for the EU necessitates composite approaches that integrate multiple methodologies. Combining diverse analytical tools and data sources enables a more holistic and precise picture of the technological state of play. This multifaceted approach enhances the ability of policymakers to derive actionable insights, ensuring that strategic decisions are grounded in robust evidence.

Embedding TMA within the EU's policy cycles, including evaluation, is crucial for ensuring that insights are not only generated but also utilised effectively. By integrating regular, long-term monitoring processes into policymaking routines, there is a higher likelihood that the insights will inform decisions before technologies fully emerge.

To sustain these efforts, it is essential to develop a centralised organisational structure dedicated to collect, analyse and push the outputs of TMA into European policy implementation. While networks of practice facilitate the sharing of best practices, methodologies, and data, they need to be complemented by an explicit reflection into the destination of the TMA initiatives. A shared platform could ensure that the insights gained are disseminated widely and integrated into various policy and decision-making frameworks, such as in the structures of the framework programmes and in the strategic reflections across policy areas.

Such a structure should have access to the higher instance of political priority setting. Both the US and China have developed systems rooted in the expertise of their respective organisations that have the mission to inform policymakers at the highest level directly.

However, such and complex monitoring cannot function without a **consistent and coherent policy approach to technology monitoring, where efforts to scan for emerging trends are followed all the way up to the choices made in selecting the promising technologies and their deployment.** The best way forward would be to **have a single owner of this monitoring work** coordinating its dissemination to the concerned actors such as legislators and policies such as R&I and industrial policies.

In conclusion, the future of TMA and anticipatory governance lies in adopting composite methodologies, embedding monitoring within policy cycles and framework programmes and **coalescing the multitude of short-term, competing initiatives into a long-term one serving the European vision, and supporting the coordination across multiple policy areas.** These strategies would collectively ensure that emerging technologies are not only

identified early but are effectively managed and integrated into society, paving the way for sustainable and inclusive technological progress, while maintaining a competitive edge for Europe in an evolving world.

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This policy brief focusses on technology monitoring and assessment (TMA). TMA is important for R&I policy orientation, and has significant socioeconomic impacts, especially in terms of emerging technologies. After outlining the advantages and features of TMA systems, this brief compares the TMA systems in China, the US and the EU, and outlines the structural and methodological challenges faced by the EU TMA approach. This brief concludes by providing recommendations to EU policymakers to transform the EU TMA system into a distinct advantage in the competition for global innovation leadership.

Research and Innovation policy

